

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF GENETIC VARIATION OF POTATO (*SOLANUM TUBEROSUM* L.): PHENOLOGICAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract

The study conducted phenological, agrobiological, and biochemical evaluations on 50 potato genotypes. The results presented the mean values, standard errors (SE), standard deviations (SD), and coefficients of variation (CV%) for each trait in a table. The trait with the highest coefficient of variation was the average tuber weight (CV=35), while the trait with the lowest coefficient of variation was sugar content (CV=0.3). Significant positive correlations were found between traits, particularly between plant height and average tuber weight ($r=0.885$) and between plant height and tuber weight per plant ($r=0.536$). The genotypes were grouped into four main clusters in the dendrogram. The primary focus of the research was the selection and planting of potato varieties suited to local conditions. High-yielding potato samples, such as SF22, SF23, SF9, SF27, SF30, SF17, SF29, SF42, and SF28, were selected based on the established criteria for high yields.

Keywords: Potato, phenological, morphological, biochemical, correlation, yield

Intruduction

Potatoes are a valuable agricultural crop and are considered one of the main food products. The high importance of potatoes is confirmed by the constant demand and expansion of its production. To develop varieties with more stable yields, it is important to identify traits associated with yield. There are a number of studies in this direction in the literature. Thus, in barley, a relationship between agronomic traits and yield was noted, which led to the conclusion that it is possible to use phenotypic relationships between yield and agronomic traits of plants to increase crop yields under sustainable production conditions [2, 4]. It was found that rice yield was significantly and positively correlated with plant height, number of grains per panicle, percentage of full grains and grain weight [10]. Studies of corn have shown significant correlations of yield with plant height, spike height, spike length, spike rows, kernels per row, kernels per spike, spike diameter, cob diameter, and 1000-kernel weight [8]. The analysis of the contribution of each agronomic trait to soybean productivity showed that the number of branches, the number

of filled pods, the number of seeds per plant, the weight of 100 seeds and the weight of seeds per plant had a positive correlation value with yield. At the same time, the number of seeds per plant had a high positive, direct effect on yield. Plant height, the number of branches, fresh weight and dry weight had an indirect effect on yield. Based on the result, it is recommended to use the number of seeds per plant as one of the selection criteria in the soybean breeding program to obtain a high-yielding variety [5].

A number of similar studies have been conducted on other agricultural crops. Since the success of selection depends to a large extent on the knowledge of the patterns of yield formation, the aim of our research was to identify the relationship between the elements of the structure and the yield of potatoes.

Material and Methods

The study used 50 local and introduced potato genotypes. Phenological, morphological, and biochemical assessments were conducted on 5 randomly selected stem tubers. The study examined

characteristics such as maturity duration, plant height, number of tubers, tuber weight, total tuber weight per plant, nitrate, dry matter, sugar, and extractive substances. These characteristics were evaluated based on the international descriptor.

Phenological Assessment

Maturity duration (days): The number of days from when the potato tubers are planted in the soil until harvest is determined by calculating the total days elapsed.

Morphological Assessment

Plant height (cm): The height of five plants was measured, and the average value was calculated.

Number of tubers (count): The tubers of each of the five plants were counted separately, and the average value was calculated.

Tubers' weight (g): The weight of five tubers was measured using a precise scale, and the average value was calculated.

Tubers' total weight per plant (g): The weight of the tubers from each of the five plants was measured separately, and the average value was calculated.

Biochemical Assessment

Nitrate (mg/kg): Nitrate levels were measured using a SOEX Nitromer device by soaking five tubers for the analysis.

Dry matter (%): A 20 g sample of tubers was dried in a thermostat device at 105°C for 24 hours to determine the dry matter percentage.

Sugar (%): The sugar content was measured by taking samples from a homogenous mixture using a pipette and performing 5 measurements on a hand-held refractometer.

Extractive substances (%): The extractive substances were measured from a homogenous mixture using a pipette, and 5 measurements were taken with an Atago brand refractometer.

Statistical Assessment

IBM SPSS software (version 25.0) was used to perform correlation analysis of morphological characters. Cluster analysis was performed using the Euclidean method in PAST software (version 4.11) to group genotypes based on their phenological, morphological and biochemical characteristics (Hammer et al. 2001).

Results

The mean values, standard deviation (SD), standard error (SE), and coefficient of variation (CV%) for the studied traits are presented in table 1.

Standard errors, which are statistical indicators of signs, are calculated. The standard error between genotypes for ripening period is 1.8, plant height is 1.2, the number of tubers is 1.4, the average weight of one tuber is 8.5, the weight of tubers per plant is 2.2, the nitrate content is 7.8, dry matter is 0.3, and sugar content and extractive substances are 0.1.

Table 1. Statistical indicators of the studied signs

	MD	PH	NT	TW	TTWP	N	DM	S	ES
Standard Error (SE)	1.8	1.2	1.4	8.5	2.2	7.8	0.3	0.1	0.1
Standard Deviation (SD)	12.8	8.4	10.1	59.8	1.41	54.9	1.9	0.6	0.7
Variance (CV)	16	7	10	35	20	30	3.7	0.3	0.5
Range	51.0	36.7	7.5	32.0	6682.2	347.4	7.1	2.9	3.3
Minimum	61.0	36.0	6.5	68.5	326.4	75.6	18.3	2.4	2.8
Maximum	112.0	72.7	8	388.5	3008.5	423.0	25.4	5.3	6.1

Maturity Duration (MD), Plant Height (PH), Number of Tubers (NT), Tuber Weight (TW), Total Tuber Weight per Plant (TTWP), Nitrate (N), Dry Matter (DM), Sugar (S), Extractive Substances (ES)

The standard deviation from the average for the second statistical indicator is 12.8 for the ripening time, 8.4 for the height of the plant, 10.1 for the number of tubers, 59.8 for the average weight of the tuber, 1.41 for the mass of tubers per plant, 54.9 for nitrates. content, dry matter - 1.9, sugar content - 0.6, extractive substances - 0.7.

Each of the studied traits showed high genetic variability. Among the traits, the highest coefficient of variation was the average tuber weight trait (CV=35), and the lowest coefficient of variation was the sugar content index (CV=0.3). The nitrate content was CV=30, the weight of tubers per plant was CV=20, the ripening time was CV=16, the number of tubers was CV=10, the plant height was CV=7, the dry matter was CV=3.7, and the coefficient of variation of extractive substances was CV=0.5.

The correlation between the two parameters was computed (Table 2). Correlation analysis can provide valuable information about the most important features when evaluating genotypes. By identifying traits that demonstrate a significant correlation, one can predict the advantage of one trait over another, and this can facilitate the selection of suitable genotypes.

Some of the traits we studied showed significant interdependence to such an extent that they could be used in selection programs. A highly reliable ($r=0.885$) correlation was established between plant height and average tuber weight. A highly significant ($r=0.536$) correlation was also observed between plant height and tuber weight per plant. A highly reliable correlation is established between the number of tubers and the mass of tubers in one plant at $r=0.700$. A highly significant positive correlation was established between the amount of nitrates and dry matter with $r=0.448$. A very significant relationship between the amount of sugar and the extractive substance $r=-0.696$ was established.

Table 2. Indicators of dependence between the studied features

	PH	NT	TW	TTWP	N	DM	S	ES
MD	0.228	-0.129	0.191	0.056	-0.075	-0.110	0.278	0.186
PH	1	-0.065	0.855**	0.536**	-0.050	-0.064	0.121	-0.040
NT		1	0.080	0.700**	-0.091	-0.157	-0.207	-0.120
TW			1	0.763**	-0.048	-0.085	0.022	-0.074
TTWP				1	-0.095	-0.177	-0.133	-0.135
N					1	0.448**	-0.171	0.180
DM						1	0.011	0.218
S							1	0.696**

The cluster analysis was compiled according to the Euclidean genetic distance index using the UPGMA method of the PAST statistical program package. Since the studied genotypes were grouped into 4 main clusters according to the specified characteristics, the dendrogram was divided into 4 clusters and analyzed accordingly (Fig. 1).

Potato genotypes FS28 and FS45 are located in the first cluster of the dendrogram. This cluster included genotypes with medium and high size in terms of ripening, with low and high indicators in plant height, with low and high indicators in the number of tubers, with low and high indicators in average weight. tuber, genotypes that showed high values of tuber mass in the plant, that showed low values of nitrate content, genotypes that showed low values of dry matter, that showed medium and low values of sugar content, as well as genotypes that showed low levels of extractive substance.

In the second cluster of the dendrogram, 3 genotypes were grouped. This cluster includes genotypes with medium and high ripening time, high plant height, and medium tuber number, genotypes that showed high values for average tuber weight, genotypes that showed average values of tuber weight per plant. Genotypes with low and average indicators of nitrate content, with low, average and high indicators of

the mass of dry matter, genotypes with average indicators of sugar content, and also genotypes with average indicators of the amount of extractive substances are included here.

The third cluster of the dendrogram included 17 genotypes. This cluster included genotypes with low, medium and high ripening periods, with medium plant height, medium number of tubers, with high average tuber weight, genotypes that showed average tuber weight per plant, with low and medium nitrate content, with medium and high dry matter weight, with medium sugar content, as well as genotypes that showed average extractive content.

The fourth cluster of the dendrogram contains seventeen genotypes. Genotypes with low and medium sizes of ripening period, with medium values of plant height, with low values of the number of tubers are united in this cluster, genotypes characterized by average indicators of tuber mass, with average tuber weight per plant, and also genotypes characterized by low and medium values of nitrate content, which showed medium and high values of dry matter content, genotypes, medium values of sugar content, medium values of extractive substances.

The main direction of our research was the selection and planting of regional varieties of potatoes taking into account local conditions, since the yield of varieties is significantly affected by growing conditions.

Fig 1 Grouping of potato genotypes based on the Euclidean index.

One of the most important factors is planting. Obtaining high-quality and productive potatoes depends on a combination of healthy seeds of the correct physiological age, a suitable seedbed and careful planting. Our studies were also carried out according to the specified rules for obtaining high yields. Taking into account the correlation we established between the average yield of one plant and the average weight of one tuber, potato samples SF22, SF23, SF9, SF27, SF30, SF17, SF29, SF42, SF28 were selected, which had a high yield.

Discussion

In the literature, there is information about the correlation dependence between some signs and productivity in potatoes. It is known that varietal and ecological differences, as well as their interaction, have a significant impact on the yield of tubers and the properties of potatoes [9] Mishra et al [6] reported significant positive correlations of common tuber yield parameters at both genotypic and phenotypic levels. The authors report that studying the magnitude of correlations between yield parameters in potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a prerequisite for identifying traits that will be useful for selection in any breeding program [6].

In the process of studying potatoes, Turkish researchers conducted cluster analysis to assess the similarity between potato genotypes. Based on the obtained dendrogram, it was found that the studied material has a huge variation [3]. The correlation coefficients showed a significant positive relationship between the number of tubers per plant, tuber yield per plot, average tuber weight, plant height, leaf area and number of stems [7]. Cluster analysis conducted Ahmadzadeh et al.[1], based on all the characteristics of 22 potato varieties, combined the genotypes into two groups. The first cluster included varieties that were characterized in the analysis of the main characteristics as potato varieties with excellent yields.

Taking into account the correlation we established between the average yield of one plant and the average weight of one tuber, potato samples were selected, which had a high yield.

The study of various characteristics of 50 local and introduced potato samples allowed to reveal a large diversity of studied potato genotypes. These assessments can help breeders select genotypes with desired characteristics for inclusion in breeding programs.

Conclusion

The study performed comprehensive analyses of phenological and biochemical traits among potato genotypes, revealing the correlations, variability, and clustering of these genotypes. Selecting appropriate genotypes for high yield and quality is crucial. The results indicate a strong relationship between plant height and tuber weight, which is an important indicator in the selection process. Identifying potato varieties with uneven yield characteristics provides valuable information for choosing genotypes suited to local conditions, aiding the selection of the most productive and high-quality varieties for cultivation.

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